

The Key Parameter of the 8T and Variational Manifolds

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Abstract:

By analyzing the idea of encompassing a manifold by the parameter $s = (M, g)$, it becomes clear that the definition of M varies as well. Author took it for granted in the 8T thesis. However to avoid confusion among readers, the shift in the meaning of M will be analyzed. In particular, M in the 8T is not the manifold but rather the space meditating the relation between the flow and the manifold. That is because the manifold was parametrized by the new element. That space is the metric tensor, assumed smooth and connected.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $S = S_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the metric tensor, given by the conditions on equation (1.3).

The manifold in the 8T is associated with the term "s".

$$s = (M, g) \tag{1}$$

That is different from the representation of manifolds in mathematical literature which regard the manifold to be the term M . Since we allocated the term "s" to the manifold, for the moment we do not have any definition of M . We invoked the manifold to be stationary, which was easier to do with the parameter "s" by the EL operator.

$$\mathcal{L} = (s, s', t) \tag{1.1}$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} - \left(\frac{d}{dt} \right) \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} = 0 \tag{1.2}$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1.3)$$

We know that the right term, $\partial g / \partial t$, of the left chain expression is the Ricci flow. The manifold is regarded to be "s" and so the M than is than the space which mediate the relation in between the Ricci flow and the manifold "s". That space is than the matric tensor, assumed to be smooth and connected. Using that extra parameter makes the process of using the EL operator easier to understand the whole construction. Equation (1.3) than reads the following varying terms, length to manifold, manifold to matric, matric to flow, flow to time. Equation (1.3) also comes to an agreement with Einstein theory and the equivalence principle as presented in (1.31):

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1.31)$$

Because we allocate an additional parameter, i.e. "s" as the manifold in the 8T, M than becomes the matric, and g is the flow. In mathematical literature M is the manifold and g is the matric tensor. The author took that change in meaning as granted by the main equation and thus did not write about it up to this day, however it is important in order to avoid confusion among readers. As readers may be familiar to the formal ideas and definitions and as a result can get confused. In particular, if they regard the second term as varying manifold-to-manifold. Summing up, the change in meaning is due to the additional parameter "s" combined with the Euler LaGrange operator. In the upcoming version of 8T thesis, this shift in meaning will be emphasized.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)